

Research

Functions of Moringa Leaves for Health Reviewed from Social and Community Aspects

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Abstract: Moringa leaves have so many benefits and are a medicinal plant that has benefits from various aspects and also various uses that are used by the community. The question in this article is: How do moringa leaves function in terms of health and social aspects? The method used is a qualitative method using a literature study. The results of the study found that moringa leaves have such great health benefits that it is proven that many diseases can be cured by consuming moringa leaves, and it also turns out that moringa leaves can also provide prevention from disease. Apart from that, moringa leaves have benefits in terms of public health aspects, namely social aspects, and also existing community aspects because moringa leaves are part of society and have been integrated into society. Health aspects, social aspects, and community aspects are important for moringa leaves and are an important part of the function and benefits of moringa leaves. What is inside moringa leaves has ethnic and regional philosophy and meaning, which is called social and cultural meaning. Moringa leaves are also related to the development of good products for the development of moringa leaves as a food source, which is related to the good nutritional aspects of moringa leaves. And one thing that is also important is the aspect of preserving moringa leaves by developing the use of moringa leaves.

Keywords: Moringa leaves, health, culture, function, ethnic, and meaning.

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Introduction

If we see that moringa leaves are a leaf that has various benefits and uses, it is very important. So if moringa leaves are used as a literature study, it will be quite interesting to see what the beneficial functions of moringa leaves actually are. Of course, in this case, what we will look at is the social aspect, which we will also look at, pay attention to, and also explain what aspects make moringa leaves so beneficial for health. Of course, this is a very interesting study from the perspective of health anthropology and also from the health communication aspect. It is very interesting to study and explain from various journals and also existing literature, which will of course look at the various existing aspects. This is very important so that existing studies and literature can be clarified and explored more deeply so that people know how important the moringa plant truly is, which will certainly provide enormous benefits to the health of the

community. Indonesia itself is a country that is rich in types of medicinal plants, one of which is moringa leaves, which are called a magical tree because of the benefits they have (1). If you look at the Moringa leaves themselves, they can grow in the lowlands at an altitude of 700 meters above sea level. This plant is 7 to 11 meters high, easy to care for, and does not require complicated care. It comes from sub-Himalayan India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Afghanistan (1). In Indonesia itself, moringa leaves are also used as a vegetable mixed with other vegetables, and currently, moringa leaves are used in preparations such as pudding and other snacks, but for health purposes, they are often used as herbal tea or medicine (1). Plants that function to prevent various diseases contain antioxidants (1). From the study above, we can see that moringa leaves have been used by the community and also have a very important function for health, which of course is important, and it is also hoped that the benefits of moringa leaves can be useful for society and also for health. Moringa leaves are an important part of people's daily lives and are an inseparable part of complete health, and the various aspects of moringa leaves are in accordance with the various aspects of existing people's lives. And it turns out that moringa leaves can be used as a medicine for anemia (2). Of course, this is a benefit obtained from moringa leaves, which is a plant that has extraordinary benefits obtained from eating moringa leaves. And in consuming moringa leaves, it is by consuming moringa leaves from clear leaves to consume moringa leaves (2), and this is what often happens and is used in consuming moringa leaves as a product (2). Moringa leaves are a processed product that is important to make into a product (2).

Processed moringa leaf products are certainly a very appropriate choice for various products rather than obtaining various preparations from existing moringa leaves so that they become an ingredient that is good for health and food that is good for health. Of course, these innovations need to be developed to achieve good health, and they are extraordinary for health. One form that is used is to use moringa leaves as a processed product that is useful for the community by using moringa leaves for processed products (3). So this makes moringa leaves widely used for various products that are useful to many people. There are various processed products that have a health impact on society. Moringa leaves are leaves that function as herbal plants (4); their benefits are diabetes, medicine for inflammation, ulcers, cancer, and also medicine for acne (4). Moringa leaves provide medicine for coconut, inflamed wounds, canker sores, fever, canker sores, medicine for scabies, and to control blood sugar. Moringa leaves also control cholesterol.

Moringa leaves are a food and traditional medicine that can be used as an antioxidant and antimicrobial (5). Can provide as part of the antioxidants that are very important for good health. For good health, antioxidants are very important for health, as part of the health of health. The question of this article is how the function and use of moringa leaves is a herbal medicinal plant originating from ethnic groups. The hypothesis raised is that this moringa plant is a plant that is well known in Indonesia and is a plant that is used for various health and also social and community functions with various uses. The functions of moringa leaves are very productive for use by the community with various uses. When viewed, it turns out that moringa leaves are widely used as medicinal plants. This is because the source of nutrients in moringa leaves is used as a medicinal tea drink and moringa leaves can also be used as an antidote from spirits(6). Of course, this does not explain that there are so many benefits of moringa leaves seen from the benefits of drinks and also from social and health functions. Moringa leaves are utilized with various functions such as the use of moringa leaves for industry and also medicine for industries such as cosmetics in which they are used starting from the roots of seeds and also the stems of moringa leaves Of course it is also used as animal feed other than that moringa leaves are also used as a custom in marriage(6). The main thing is actually moringa leaves have benefits especially for public health as a medicinal plant(7). From the descriptions presented above, it illustrates that there are so many benefits obtained from moringa leaves for the community that the hypothesis presented becomes a good argument to provide a hypothesis and also from the arguments given earlier provides a strong argument for the hypothesis presented.

Method

The method used in this article is a qualitative method that involves carrying out a literature study process. So that it provides an overview of the objects studied in this article, meaning it provides an overview of the benefits of moringa leaves for health. What has been done is to look for literature related to the problem of this article to support and provide an overview of the literature and studies in this article.

Results and Discussion

In accordance with the literature obtained, it turns out that it is true that moringa leaves have great benefits for people's health and provide goodness for society. The health benefits contained in them are related to traditional medicine. Moringa leaves are a traditional medicine that has good benefits for health and contains things that are good for health, such as calcium, vitamin C, and protein, by consuming extracts from moringa leaves (8). Moringa leaves themselves are a plant that grows a lot in Indonesia and grows a lot in home gardens in Indonesia (8). It is clear that moringa leaves have the property of increasing the human body's immunity, and processing moringa leaves can also be done in very simple ways (8). What is interesting from the study above is that moringa shows an identification system (9). Moringa leaves are leaves that are well known among Indonesian people and have enormous benefits, and it turns out that cultivating moringa leaves does not require special care (9). And also, no one has used moringa leaves for products made from moringa leaves (9). The classification of existing medicinal plants is certainly very interesting to see and study.

With the classification of medicinal plants, it becomes interesting so that it brings goodness and becomes a strength to carry out various aspects that give strength to the health of the existing community, which shows goodness and public health. The existence of moringa leaves, which shows the male element and also the female element in Moringa leaves, makes them an inseparable part of human life, which shows that the various separations that exist are caused by the meanings contained in the moringa leaves (9). It turns out that moringa leaves have a symbolic meaning that is quite interesting when studied in the context of social sciences, which provides a very large social and cultural meaning and has a very important meaning in the context of social sciences. Moringa leaves can be used in various processed products, such as noodles, nuggets, and noodles (10). What was done was a development to make moringa leaves into a product (10).

Moringa leaves have benefits for various foods that are used for food (11). And it turns out that moringa leaves have quite extraordinary uses in terms of health and provide very important effects on health. Among the diseases that can be cured are weight loss, treating internal diseases, treating cancer, ringworm, healthy hair, healthy eyes, and preventing disease heart(11). Apart from that, it can also preserve the environment and bring beauty (11). And it turns out that moringa leaves also have excellent nutritional value, which, of course, provides many benefits for the community. Nutritional content is very necessary for growth, especially for children, who have a lot of needs for plants that contain fiber, especially in relation to the nutrition obtained from these foods. The addition of moringa leaves turns out to have very good nutritional benefits and is also best related to the various proteins and minerals contained in this food product (12). It is from this aspect that it is very important to make reference to various food products that are very good for health and also contain various content elements that are good for health. Moreover, the Indonesian nation has various kinds of products that are good for health and the human body. This needs to be developed starting from the village and also from various kinds of activities in the community that can be used as a strength to make nutritious products that are made. from the moringa leaves. So it can be said that moringa leaves have enormous health benefits by making them a food product.

The creativity of the moringa plant can be used as a herbal drink (13), which leads to the optimization of the moringa leaves. What is certain is that if we look at the use of moringa leaves in various herbal products (13), it will certainly bring benefits to society. We understand that our society is one that really likes drinks; even tea is a drink that is always consumed and drunk by our people. Of course, providing health benefits by consuming tea containing various herbal plants can benefit our society. So the principles used are to make health drinks a part of life, which will certainly provide benefits to our society. People who make health a part of their lives thus indirectly provide enormous benefits to the community and also to the general public regarding the benefits of this herbal plant. By doing this, it will indirectly provide really big benefits for health and also benefits for society.

And it turns out that people have processed moringa leaves into tea or drinks where the benefits are for treating hypertension, strengthening bones, producing breast milk, anti-aging, skin care, and treating diabetes (14). Of course, this is the basis for the fact for the fact that the moringa plant has important uses, such as processed moringa chips, coffee, and tea, which are foods and drinks in demand by Indonesian people (14). It turns out that there are so many benefits to be gained from moringa leaves that an effort needs to be made to always pay attention, spread moringa as a food and drink, and make it a mainstay for the Indonesian people. With this utilization, it will certainly provide community aspects that will bring financial benefits to the community. This means that moringa leaves have enormous benefits for society and also for our economy. This is also a big challenge for the benefit and also for the health and economy of the Indonesian nation. This is a great strength, and our nation always develops the various medicinal plants they have.

This means that the literature presented above gives an important meaning to moringa leaves as an herbal plant that has many benefits. The benefits felt are like moringa leaves as a medicinal plant and also products that are very important for health. Apart from that, moringa leaves are also used for beauty products and for various other products, such as food products that can be used for nutritious food and also provide health benefits. Therefore, it is very important to preserve moringa leaves for the health of our people. Preservation is very important because, by preserving these medicinal plants, they will then become products that will survive in our society. This preservation is important to obtain benefits from the moringa plant because the plant must be preserved and also used for the benefit of society and for the good effects on the body from eating moringa leaves. Moringa leaves, which provide enormous benefits for people's health, are the main thing that must be done to obtain the various benefits felt and also for the health of our people.

When referring to expert views, this includes the domain of ethnomedicine (15). This means that this treatment is a treatment that comes from herbal leaves and is part of ethnic-based medicine. This means that this is included as a treatment that is said to be traditional medicine. This traditional medicine is an inseparable part and has also become something that has been practiced by our society. These ethnic-based treatments are treatments that have been used for thousands of years by our ancestors. Treatment that leads to health and also to the practice of the various traditions that we have. This means that this is ethnomedicine (15), which is part of the medicine that has become a tradition in our society. There are so many functions of these medicinal plants that bring health and are also part of the traditions of our society. Ethnic-based medicine is treatment that is based on traditions that have developed and have become a practice for the community. And it has become a treatment that our society relies on and has brought health to our society ever since.

And it turns out that this herbal-based treatment has become something important and has even spread not only to beliefs but also to social media (16). This is important and happens in our society; herbal medicine is a very important

treatment for society. And nowadays, it doesn't just spread to society in a good way; it also reaches society through social media. The use of social media in the development of social media also provides benefits to the development of society through the use of traditional medicine that develops in social media. The use of social media is very important for society. The use of social media is important nowadays because it provides an image of health and development. The use of traditional medicine is becoming well developed by utilizing herbal plants, which bring benefits to mothers (17). The use of herbal plants that provide benefits to mothers means that mothers get the benefits of existing herbal plants. The role of mothers here is very important in the use of herbal medicinal plants, which provide benefits for mothers. So moringa leaves become food for mothers and their families, and of course, this increases production from our hands with guaranteed nutrition. This means that moringa is a leaf that is used by mothers and will also provide benefits to many people with its nutritional content. The community has a very important role in society and provides good health for health and brings good health and provides very important benefits for society. Apart from that, what we do is an inseparable part of our community health and is a very important part of our society.

Moringa leaves have benefits related to nutritional problems contained in them (18). And also, moringa leaves are a very important plant and have many uses and properties as a source of medicines (18). They are used as medicines and to prevent various dangerous diseases (18). So moringa leaves are widely used as fresh vegetables (18). Of course, the many benefits of moringa leaves provide great benefits for our society to make the best use of moringa leaves for the health of the community and provide happiness to many people. Moringa leaves provide various benefits and have various uses for society and our health. And it turns out that, from the results of the community, it was found that moringa leaves are a health plant that can cure Kinder by regularly drinking moringa leaves.

Processed catfish and moringa leaves apparently provide quite a large nutritional content, providing economic and health benefits (19). This is a very important thing to explain regarding the benefits obtained from processed catfish and moringa leaves for the food needs of our society. By processing moringa leaves with various other products, it will certainly provide considerable benefits for our society and bring goodness and economic benefits to the people and residents of our nation. These things certainly need to be developed and continue to be encouraged and provided for the good of the nation and society at large, with various uses obtained from the use of moringa leaves in these high-quality food products.

It turns out that the use of moringa leaves is also important for improving nutrition to prevent stunting (20). This is, of course, very supportive of not using moringa leaves to prevent stunting in society. There are still many cases of stunting that occur in our society and also require very serious treatment. It is not certain that the use of moringa leaves can provide benefits and also provide a program to overcome existing stunting. Moringa leaves have so many benefits and uses that they can prevent this problem in our society. And moringa leaves themselves are easily found in yards and locations in Indonesia. So it is very economical to help our community get good nutrition so that we can overcome stunting in the community. Indonesian society must get rid of this stunting problem, and we also have to get rid of this problem. Of course, what is needed is the use of herbal plants that exist in our society. So with this, provide effective solutions to deal with stunting and also provide all solutions by using moringa leaves.

And not only that, moringa leaves are also a plant that can be made into healthy cookies, which are a superior product (21). Of course, these innovations provide food diversity, various types of food that cannot be used for food, and nutritional content for children. Because we are still very lacking in getting nutrition and being owned and desired by children, this innovation will certainly provide many benefits and also for health in society, especially for children. Children need all the nutritional value-added foods they can find, and of course, this product provides great benefits

for providing good nutritional content for children. With these various preparations, it will provide benefits and goodness to our society, lead course, dness and also good production for our society, especially for fulfilling children's nutrition. and of course this is very popular with children and adults alike. So that the fulfillment of nutrition as well as the content of malnutrition will provide enormous benefits by utilizing the food production that we have. This will lead to goodness and also good production for our society, especially for fulfilling children's nutrition.

One of the important things is the use of media in health communication (22). This means that Moringa leaves will have enormous benefits if marketed through existing media. This means that it is related to health communication to develop Moringa leaves so that they are owned by the community. It is very important to provide understanding to the local community about the importance of consuming moringa leaves. Moringa leaves are leaves that the Indonesian people need to develop and know about throughout society and become consumed by. Because of the literature stated above, it turns out that moringa leaves have enormous functions and benefits for society. And moringa leaves have great nutrition and also have a huge impact on our society. And also, moringa leaves are leaves that have been known for a long time by our people and are part of our community life. So that aspects of the media and its development need to be expanded through the media, the meaning of health communication provides enormous benefits for our society and also provides great benefits for society.

Conclusion

The conclusion of this article is that moringa leaves have a very high social aspect, which contains cultural and health aspects. From the existing literature, it turns out that Moringa is a medicinal plant that exists in our society and is also used for the health of our society. And preparations from moringa leaves are widely used as traditional medicine, which originates from the ancestors of the Indonesian people. Also, moringa leaves have a personalistic meaning (15) in the world of medicine and not only a naturalistic meaning (15) in them. Moringa leaves are a leaf that is widely used, has very high nutritional value, has a lot of symbolic meaning, and is also used for beauty and for hand products that have high value. Of course, there are many important aspects of moringa leaves that make them important, namely that Moringa leaves are an important element of the culture of society in our society and are part of the treasury of Indonesian society with the various functions contained in moringa leaves. This is and becomes part of the nation's culture and the strength that exists in the nation's culture.

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